

The Stability of Beryllium Complexes with Organic Ligands.

I. Salicylaldehyde and Related Ligands

P. CHARAN DAS & G. S. RAO

Chemistry Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay-85

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The stability constants of the complexes of Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Al^{3+} with salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxy-acetophenone, methyl salicylate, salicylamide and salicylic acid in 50% dioxan-water medium at 35° and at an ionic strength of 0.3M have been determined. The effect of composition of the medium on the pK values and the stability constants of beryllium complexes has been studied. A correction for hydrolysis of beryllium was applied in calculating the stability constants of its complexes. It has been found that the stability of complexes of these ions increases in the order $\text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Be}^{2+} < \text{Al}^{3+}$.

Amongst divalent ions, beryllium by virtue of its small ionic radius and high charge is expected to form strong complexes. Numerous complexes of beryllium with organic ligands containing oxygen donors such as β -diketones, tropolones, hydroxy acids, etc., have been reported and their stability constants determined¹. However, very little data is available on complexes of beryllium with phenolic ligands such as salicylaldehyde and related compounds. In the present study the stability constants of beryllium complexes with salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxy acetophenone, methylsalicylate, salicylamide and salicylic acid have been determined, so as to study the effect of substitution in the ligand. The stability constants of the complexes have been determined in 50% (v/v) dioxan-water medium since the ligands are sparingly soluble in water. The effect of varying the composition of the medium on the pK values of the ligands and the stability constants of beryllium complexes has been studied. Beryllium, magnesium and aluminium form a triad of small ions exhibiting a degree of similarity. Therefore, the stabilities of the complexes of magnesium and aluminium have also been studied for the purpose of comparison. The results show that the stabilities increase as $\text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Be}^{2+} < \text{Al}^{3+}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. Salicylaldehyde was distilled under vacuum and the fraction distilling at 55° was collected. Salicylamide was recrystallized from aqueous ethanol (m.p. found 140°). Carbonate free sodium hydroxide was prepared by the standard method². Dioxan was purified by the method of Riddick and Toops³.

A stock solution of beryllium perchlorate was prepared by dissolving beryllium hydroxide in excess perchloric acid. The free acid was estimated by passing the solution through a cation exchanger in the H^+ form. Beryllium was estimated gravimetrically as oxide². From the concentrations of beryllium and total perchloric acid, the free acid was calculated.

The stock solutions of salicylaldehyde and *o*-hydroxy acetophenone in dioxan were analysed for carbonyl group as 2-4 dinitrophenyl hydrazone⁴. Methylsalicylate was estimated by hydrolyzing with sodium hydroxide and titrating the unused alkali⁴. Aluminium was estimated gravimetrically as 8-hydroxy quinotinate and magnesium was estimated by titrating with EDTA using erio-chrome black T as an indicator².

The *pH* titrations were carried out in a glass cell with a jacket for circulating water from a thermostat maintained at 35°. Nitrogen free from carbon dioxide, washed and presaturated with the solution to be titrated was used to maintain an inert atmosphere. Beckman Model G *pH* meter standardized with buffers of *pH* 4.02 and 9.10 was used. The *pH* readings were accurate within ± 0.05 .

For each set of experiments, three titrations were carried out adopting Irving-Rossotti method⁵. Solutions containing : (1) free mineral acid (0.01 *M*); (2) free mineral acid + ligand (0.05 *M*); and (3) free mineral acid + ligand + metal ion (0.01 *M*) were titrated with a standard solution of sodium hydroxide. The initial volume of the solution was 40.0 ml and an ionic strength of 0.3 *M* was maintained by the addition of sodium perchlorate since the rate of change of activity coefficient with ionic strength is small⁶. \bar{n}_a , \bar{n} and p_L were calculated to determine the *pK* values and the stability constants, K_1 and K_2 of the complexes. In the medium employed, i.e., 50% (v/v) dioxan, the *pH* meter reading does not give the true hydrogen ion concentration and hence the *pK* values are practical dissociation constants⁵.

The concentration of metal ions chosen permitted the study of hydrolysis of beryllium. In a system containing metal ion and ligand the hydrolysis of complexed and free metal ion can occur. However, the former will be significant only at very high *pH* values. The hydrolysis correction was applied following the method developed by Nair⁷, and the free metal ion in the system was calculated using Newton's method of approximation⁸.

The experimental conditions employed for studying the effect of composition of the medium were slightly different. The concentrations of metal ion, ligand and perchloric acid were 0.001, 0.005 to 0.007, 0.01 *M* respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I gives the titration data for the salicylaldehyde systems of the metal ions Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Al^{3+} . \bar{n}_{max} and \bar{n}'_{max} values calculated from the data for beryllium systems with

Symbols used in the text

\bar{n}_{max} = maximum value of \bar{n} .

\bar{n}'_{max} = maximum value of \bar{n} obtained after applying hydrolysis correction.

n_x = mole fraction of dioxan in the medium.

K_1, K_2 = stepwise stability constants of complexes.

$\Delta \log K_1$ = ratio of stability constants with substituted and unsubstituted ligands.

ΔpK = ratio of the *pK* values of substituted and unsubstituted ligands.

different ligands are generally greater than one. However, the values of \bar{n}'_{max} are smaller than \bar{n}_{max} which indicates that the effect of hydrolysis on complex formation is pronounced.

In the case of systems of magnesium with salicylaldehyde and salicylamide \bar{n}_{max} are 1.08 and 0.64 respectively, while for the *o*-hydroxy-acetophenone and methyl salicylate the values are 1.47 and 1.51 respectively. However, K_1 and K_2 could be calculated for all the systems. There was no detectable complexation between Mg^{2+} and salicylic acid.

Low concentrations of aluminium ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) and the high ligand to metal ratios are employed in the present study to suppress the hydrolysis. K_1 values for all the systems were obtained at *pH* well below 4 and only $\log K_1$ values are reported in view of the hydrolytic effects at higher *pH* values. \bar{n}_{max} for all the systems was always greater than two indicating that ML_3 was also formed. K_1 values were obtained directly from the formation curves.

If the ligands are represented by the structural formula I the *pK* values of the ligands, as may be seen from Table 2, increase for different substituents, R, as follows :

TABLE 1

Titration data of salicylaldehyde systems

Beryllium										
<i>B</i>	3.5	3.75	4.0	4.2	4.3	4.4	4.5	4.6		
\bar{n}	0.08	0.17	0.31	0.46	0.54	0.64	0.72	0.78		
\bar{n}'	0.02	0.13	0.28	0.35	0.42	0.44	0.52	0.61		
<i>pL</i>	6.91	6.66	6.42	6.23	6.14	6.05	5.95	5.86		
<i>B</i>	4.7	4.8	5.4	5.5	5.6	5.8	5.9	6.0		
\bar{n}	0.86	0.91	1.25	1.32	1.36	1.48	1.52	1.56		
\bar{n}'	0.71	0.82	1.26	1.36	1.39	1.50	1.52	1.53		
<i>pL</i>	5.76	5.67	5.09	5.00	4.90	4.71	4.62	4.52		
<i>B</i>	6.1	6.2	6.4							
\bar{n}	1.59	1.63	1.71							
\bar{n}'	1.54	1.56	1.60							
<i>pL</i>	4.42	4.33	4.13							
Magnesium										
<i>B</i>	7.0	7.5	7.75	8.0	8.25	8.5	8.6	8.7	8.8	8.9
\bar{n}	0.07	0.22	0.39	0.50	0.68	0.76	0.89	1.01	1.01	1.08
<i>pL</i>	3.41	2.92	2.68	2.44	2.20	1.97	1.87	1.77	1.68	1.58
Aluminium										
<i>B</i>	3.15	3.25	3.4	3.55	3.75	3.95	4.1	4.25	4.5	4.75
\bar{n}	0.16	0.46	0.78	1.06	1.34	1.58	1.72	2.06	2.50	2.70
<i>pL</i>	7.52	7.40	7.26	7.12	6.92	6.73	6.58	6.44	6.20	5.95

The stability of the complexes formed by the metal ions also increases in the same order showing that the donation of the electrons is determined by the basicity of the ligands. The plot of $\log K_1$ of beryllium complexes with pK of the ligands is shown in Fig. 1, curve 1, while those of magnesium and aluminium complexes are represented by curves 2 and 3 respectively. The data obtained by Aggett⁹ for the beryllium complexes with aromatic hydroxy acids have also been plotted for comparison (Fig. 1, curve 4). It is apparent that the correlations are linear and that the plots for the complexes with salicylic acid in the case of beryllium and aluminium deviate. It may be inferred from these observations that the ligands fall into two groups, viz., (1) phenolic carbonyl ligands which coordinate through the carbonyl group and (2) hydroxy acids which coordinate through carboxylate group in addition to the phenolic oxygen. The complexes formed by the ligands in the two groups can be represented, for the divalent ions, by the structural formulæ II and III which explains the observed deviation in the case of salicylic acid.

Another interesting correlation of $\Delta \log K_1$ with ΔpK similar to that obtained by Da Silva and Calado¹⁰ is shown in Fig. 2 for the metal ions in the present study. All the ligands are ortho substituted compounds and hence the ΔpK values are similar to Hammett's

Fig. 1. Correlation of $\log K_1$ with $\text{pK}(\text{OH})$ of ligands. Curves 1, 2 and 3 represent the complexes of Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Al^{3+} with salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, methyl salicylate and salicylamide. Curve 4 is a plot of Aggett's data on beryllium complexes with hydroxy acids. ●—Denote the salicylate complexes of Be^{2+} and Al^{3+} .

constants¹¹, taking into consideration that steric effects are not appreciable. In fact, the smaller size of the hydroxyl group in the present ligands compared to the carboxyl group referred to in Hammett's equation¹¹ causes less steric interaction with substituents in positions 2 and 6.¹²

Fig. 2. Correlation of $\Delta \log K_1$ with $\Delta pK(OH)$. Curves 1, 2 and 3 represent the complexes of Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Al^{3+} with salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, methylsalicylate, salicylamide and salicylic acid.

$\log K_1$ values for the complexes formed by the metal ions, Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Al^{3+} given in Table 2, show that they increase as $Mg^{2+} < Be^{2+} < Al^{3+}$, which is consistent with the Z^2/r values for these ions.

TABLE 2

Stability constants of metal ligand complexes in 50% dioxan at 35°

Ligand	H ⁺	Mg ^{2+***}		Be ^{2+***}		Al ^{3+**}
	pK	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1
Salicylaldehyde	9.2	2.3	1.4	5.9	4.6	7.4
<i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone	11.8	3.6	2.6	8.2	—	9.6
Methyl salicylate	11.3	3.6	2.6	7.4	7.0	9.2
Salicylamide	9.5	1.5	0.9	7.2	6.3	8.6
Salicylic acid	pK ₁ = 4.2 pK ₂ = 14.1	—	—	12.9	10.2	13.9

* Half integral values.

** Calculated by the method of least squares.

The pK values and stability constants of complexes obtained in 5%, 25% and 75% (v/v) dioxan are given in Table 3. The variation of pK values and $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ with n_x of dioxan in the medium can be represented by

$$\log K = an_x + b$$

where $\log K$ represents any of these quantities. The slopes (a) and intercepts (b) obtained with different ligands are given in Table 4. The results show that decrease in dielectric constant with n_x favours greater association of the ions resulting in higher K values.

TABLE 3

Stability constants of beryllium complexes in aqueous dioxan media

Ligand	5%	$\log K_1$ 25% dioxan	75%	5%	$\log K_2$ 25% dioxan	75%
Salicylaldehyde	5.4	6.2	7.8	4.3	4.8	7.4
<i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone	7.6	8.3	9.7	6.1	6.9	9.3
Salicylamide	6.3	6.6	8.5	4.9	5.8	6.6
Methylsalicylate	—	7.5	8.7	—	6.2	8.4

TABLE 4

Variation of constants with mole fraction of dioxan

$$K = an_x + b$$

Ligand	n_x range	pK		$\log K_1$		$\log K_2$	
		a	b	a	b	a	b
Salicylaldehyde	0.01—0.39	6.0	8.2	4.4	5.3	5.1	4.3
<i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone	-do-	5.5	10.2	5.4	7.7	5.9	6.0
Methylsalicylate	0.07—0.39	9.0	9.8	4.3	7.4	5.0	5.9
Salicylamide	0.01—0.39	4.0	8.6	5.5	6.2	5.0	4.65

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